

Learning ecologies as an inclusive impactful approach to increasing science literacy

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ABSTRACT

Science education should be a fundamental part of all children's habitat. Policies should empower students, teachers, parents, and the broader community by enhancing access and creating opportunities for involvement and excellence in science literacy. STE(A)M Learning Ecologies (SLEs) is an EU-funded project developing engaging open schooling-enabled science learning paths for all in learning continuums of formal and informal education settings focusing on inclusiveness. The SLEs approach is grounded in three main pillars: STE(A)M as an overarching pedagogical and content approach, Open Schooling as a way to connect schools with their communities, and Living Lab practice to foster co-creation, experimentation, and real-life relevance. In this article, we discuss the potential social impact of successfully quality science education via learning ecologies; describe the SLEs methodology as an approach to achieve this goal; and showcase lessons learned from the first phase of the project. So far, the SLEs approach has demonstrated promising results in enabling stakeholders to recognize gaps in STEAM learning opportunities—spanning content areas, age groups, and experience levels—and highlighted the importance of cross-community collaboration to address ongoing challenges.

SPECIFICATIONS TABLE (All sections are mandatory unless marked otherwise)

Subject area	3304 Education Social Sciences & Humanities
Category/categories of societal impact	Cultural Economic Education Environmental Societal Technological
Sustainable Development Goals (SDGS) the research contributes to	GOAL 4: Quality Education GOAL 5: Gender Equality GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

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GOAL 10: Reduced Inequality
GOAL 17: Partnerships to achieve the Goal

Related published article

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Ecsite 2025 Conference, 3–5 June 2025 Warsaw, Open Schooling in action: Building lasting partnerships for educational innovation, Stephanos Cherouvis - Ecsite, Alexandra Okada - Open University, Daniëlle Meuleman - Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Rony Ben-Chaim - Bloomfield Science Museum Jerusalem, Vasileios Liakopoulos - Ellinogermaniki, Agogi Laura Wanckel - International Centre for STEM Education, University of Education, Freiburg, Laura Mentini - APRE – Agency for the Promotion of European Research, Denis Saggese – Ecsite, Programme available here.

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EDULEARN 2024 - 16th annual International Conference on Education and New Learning Technologies, Palma (Spain) - 1-3 July 2024, ADDRESSING ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES THROUGH INNOVATIVE AND ENGAGING EDUCATION APPROACHES: INSIGHTS FROM HORIZON EUROPE PROJECTS, EDULEARN24, M. Castellari, L. Mentini, C. Pocaterra, K. Jurkiewicz (2024), in IATED Digital Library: <https://library.iated.org/view/CASTELLARI2024ADD>

Research Project

Based on lessons learnt from previous open schooling projects, and in close synergy with the stakeholder community, the EU-funded SLEs project develops, implements and evaluates the STE(A)M Learning Ecologies methodology, an innovative approach enabling the creation of open learning environments fostering science education opportunities for all. Experts from stakeholder communities in several countries will cooperate to implement STE(A)M learning ecologies across Europe. By emphasising inclusiveness and environmental sustainability, they will promote and facilitate the creation of partnerships among formal, non-formal and informal education institutions, as well as enterprises and the local community.

Link to the summary of the project – <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094648>

Conference Paper

ECER 2025 Belgrade, 08.09.2025, STE(A)M Learning Ecologies: A typology of open schooling projects based on stakeholder and learner engagement, T Hovardas, K Vakkou, K Arampatzi, K Stekić, Z Zacharia, L Mentini: <https://eera-ecer.de/conferences/ecer-2025-belgrade>

Official Report

SLEs methodology – First version, June 2023, Report available here - https://www.steamecologies.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/D2.2_SLEs_Methodology-Updated-Version_v3_streamlined.pdf

SLEs Infographic: Structure of a STE(A)M Learning Ecology, available here - https://www.steamecologies.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/STEAM-Learning-Ecologies_First_Infographic.pdf

Stage of research

In Progress

Societal impacts: nurturing quality science education communities

Science education plays a crucial role in improving society by fostering critical thinking, innovation, and informed decision-making. Understanding science equips people with the ability to interpret the world around them, helping individuals make informed choices about health, technology, and the environment, leading to better personal and societal outcomes [1]. Science literacy, and the integration of arts, is essential for tackling pressing global issues such as climate change, pandemics, and food security [2]. Educated individuals can contribute to solutions and support evidence-based policies to address these challenges. Moreover, science education encourages analytical thinking, experimentation, and reasoning. These skills are essential in everyday decision-making and help individuals navigate misinformation, biases, and complex societal issues. Nations with well-developed science education systems tend to have stronger economies driven by research and technological progress [3]. Thus, access to quality science education can contribute to a more knowledgeable, innovative, and responsible global community, capable of advancing toward a sustainable and prosperous future.

Quality science education should therefore be a fundamental part of compulsory education for all students. Policies should actively support students, teachers, parents, and the broader community in improving access to quality science education, fostering excellence in learning, and ensuring that young people are motivated and well-equipped to engage in scientific discourse and pursue further studies. This aligns with the vision of "opening the school" [4] to new learning experiences and collaborations with external stakeholders to enhance student learning. These educational experiences are built on local-level partnerships that connect formal, non-formal, and informal science education providers with businesses and civil society. The goal is to integrate open schooling across all education levels in science education, bridging the gap between formal and non-formal education. This approach fosters a connected science learning ecosystem where young people experience diverse opportunities supported by adults and peers, promoting

academic, professional, and civic growth. To achieve this, educators and organizations must collaborate beyond institutional boundaries to ensure equitable learning opportunities.

To contribute towards this need, the STE(A)M Learning Ecologies (SLEs) Horizon Europe project (<https://www.steamecologies.eu/>) aims to devise a novel methodology on how to nurture strong collaborations among stakeholders—including school communities, academia, research centers, families, societal actors, industries, and policy-makers—to enhance scientific knowledge and skills while promoting science at local, regional, and European levels. With a vision of creating an expansive and immersive learning network across multiple European countries, SLEs aims to continually expand their reach locally, nationally, and globally. The ecologies unite teachers, scientists, researchers, science museum professionals, enterprise experts, and other STE(A)M-related stakeholders, facilitating learning opportunities and fostering comprehensive learner engagement in STE(A)M throughout education.

Methodology: STE(A)M learning ecologies

When considering how students can thrive in such an ecosystem, the concept of learning pathways [5] emerges as a valuable framework. Pathways help structure youth experiences, enabling them to build upon their learning across different contexts—such as home, school, universities, community organizations, science centers, museums, social media, and the workplace. This enables us to see these opportunities for learning through the broader lens of the learning ecology [6]. A learning ecology encompasses the physical, social, and cultural contexts where learning takes place. The individuals within this system have distinct roles that interact with one another, shaping the work environment. While the system evolves over time, it maintains an overall sense of equilibrium—even if that equilibrium involves constant adaptation [6]. By envisioning learning ecologies—the physical, social, and cultural contexts in which learning occurs—we recognize the importance of both tangible resources (e.g., museums, science programs) and sociocultural dimensions (e.g., mentorship, collaboration). A strong science learning ecology is diverse, adaptable, and interconnected, providing multiple avenues for people to engage with science as part of a continuous learning journey. Building on this foundation, the SLEs project leverages the concept of learning ecologies to develop impactful local open schooling partnerships. This redefines open schooling to extend beyond traditional classrooms to all formal and informal learning spaces within a community. It promotes inclusive and interconnected learning

Fig. 1. Components of a STE(A)M Learning Ecology.

Fig. 2. A group working collaboratively on the development of a Virtual Reality (VR) application.

Fig. 3. The Gantt chart of one of the students’ teams for the software development project of the SLE.

opportunities for people of all ages and backgrounds—including students, lifelong learners, and the public—within STE(A)M learning ecologies.

The SLEs approach is grounded in three main pillars: STE(A)M as an overarching pedagogical and content approach, Open Schooling as a way to connect schools with their communities, and Living Lab practice to foster co-creation, experimentation, and real-life relevance. The SLEs methodology is intended to be replicable and scalable, offering a model that can be adapted across different contexts and by a variety of stakeholders. While several components—such as co-creation templates, stakeholder engagement processes, and reflection tools—are transferable across contexts, other aspects like thematic focus and local partnerships remain context-specific, allowing adaptation to local educational and societal needs. The work follows a structured process: (1) **Initiation**, where stakeholders—schools, community actors, and businesses—establish a partnership that mirrors an ecology, an environment of interconnected actors, fostering diversity and adaptability while sharing a common vision and goals; (2) **Co-Creation**, where participants collaboratively design interdisciplinary, inquiry-based learning activities that utilize STE(A)M principles in addressing real-world problems; (3) **Implementation**, during which the developed activities are implemented and further refined through iterations with students and community partners; and (4) **Reflection and evaluation**,

where processes and outcomes are assessed for impact, and insights are gathered aiming to improve future implementations.

Digital and physical co-creation spaces that facilitate active, participatory learning, living lab methodology, and open schooling practices are important tools and strategies of the SLEs methodology. The focus on **knowledge transfer** is a fundamental component, guaranteeing that activities are applicable not just to their immediate environments but also to other educational and community contexts. The SLEs methodology provides a route to more engaged, interdisciplinary learning and is a model for promoting innovation in education by integrating education with real-world, community-based concerns. The approach is adaptable across settings, offering a practical framework for educators, policymakers, and organisations aiming to build stronger connections between education, industry, and society. It provides a framework for sustainable, collaborative learning environments that evolve with educational and societal needs. Pilot implementations were evaluated through SLE initiator interviews and online reflection workshops held during and after the SLEs to capture insights on collaboration, learning experience, and inclusion.

Results and implications

In the initial phase of the SLEs project (2023–2024), we applied the

SLEs methodology to pilot ten STE(A)M Learning Ecologies across Europe, implemented in diverse geographical, educational, and cultural contexts. Participants were engaged through established networks of schools and communities, ensuring broad representation. Qualitative and quantitative data—including questionnaires, interviews, and reflection workshops—were collected to capture participants' and stakeholders' learning progression and experiences. The table below provides a summary of the ecologies implemented in this initial phase, including examples of the learning products, the number of participants in each of the ecologies, and the data collected to evaluate each ecology.

experience and the impact for each stakeholder group involved in the pilot SLE.

Students: The SLE provided significant benefits to students by fostering an inclusive and interdisciplinary learning environment that brought together individuals from diverse backgrounds. Through hands-on, project-based experiences aligned with real-world challenges, students developed essential software engineering and project management skills. Key competencies developed included requirements gathering, project planning, stakeholder negotiation, risk assessment, and expertise across the software development lifecycle. This hands-on experience enhanced students' readiness for professional roles, supporting career

Country	Type of initiator	SLE Topic	Stakeholders	No. of learners	Learners Age	Learning products
Cyprus	Policy maker	Butterflies conservation	Policy makers, school, teachers, universities, museum, municipalities	23	16 y/o	Transectes designed for recording butterflies; butterfly counts by means of the central electronic system eBMS
Germany	School	Sustainable energy for the future	School teachers, University teachers, Teachers in training and out-school	15	12–16 y/o	Hypotheses; experimental designs; small renewable energy systems and models of fuel cell-powered cars
Greece	Secondary school	Understanding Earthquakes	Secondary school, research center/university, local municipality, industry	175	13–15 y/o	Seismometers; datasets, graphs
Ireland	Community Library	Brain science and arts	Schools, Community Library, Artists, research centers	37	15 y/o	Survey items and stats; sketches of Museum and microscopy lab; Brain Mosaics
Italy	Co-initiated by a NGO, civil society and a national research agency	Circular bioeconomy	School, Universities, Government agencies	21	11 y/o	Films; articles; creative recycling solutions; nudge experiment
Malta	Policy maker	Entrepreneurship and STEAM	Policy makers, students, teachers, university, researchers, NGO, industry partners	60	12–13 y/o	Flow diagrams; entrepreneurship solutions for real world problems
Norway	University	Software engineering	University teachers and students, industry partners	65	21–24 y/o	Minimum Valuable Product (MVP); project report; presentation
Romania	Primary school	Discovering nature in the Cozia National Park	School teachers and students, National Park, Regional Theatre; County school inspectorate, local library, Parents association, NGO	21	6–7 y/o	ebook of nature; graphs; robotic models; comics; videos; bird feeder models
Serbia	Secondary school	Designing sports equipment	Gymnasium, professional sportsmen, Architect, journalist and sports commentator, quiz professional, theologian, civil society, government body for the promotion of science	450	15–19 y/o	Sketches of innovative sports equipment designs; digital 3D models; drawings; CAD models; mockups showcasing the design's physical aspects and usability; datasets; graphs
Slovakia	Secondary school	Discovering Polish/Slovak shared natural heritage and its endangered species	School teachers and students from a Polish and a Slovak school, parents, National Park	20	12–13 y/o	Herbal book on local endangered species; exhibition
Portugal	Primary School	Ecosystems and their challenges	Schools and students, research centers, science center government agency, civil society organizations, industry	188	8–10 y/o	Clay volcanoes, robots, solar clocks, painted bags, observational drawings and tables on environmental parameters
Spain	Secondary school	AI to imagine the world in 2030	Schools and students, science center, industry, festival organization, university, science clubs	11	15–16 y/o	Sketches, scripts, AI-produced audiovisual piece on the world in 2030 (connected to SDG)

An example case study

This case study was conducted in Norway and focuses on an ecology initiated by NTNU and an industry partner [7]. This learning ecology (SLE) is designed to bridge theoretical and practical knowledge in IT. The primary stakeholders are students, teachers, industry professionals, and researchers, each playing crucial roles and contributing to an interdisciplinary learning environment. In total, 65 students (21–24 years old) participated in the SLE pilot, along with 7 University teachers, 11 industry professionals. The goal of the SLE was to equip students with software engineering skills through project-based development in teams that created realistic software prototypes for real-world customers. Each team had 6–7 students that could choose their own topic within software development field in collaboration with the industry representative assigned to them. Below, you can see a short summary describing the

development and a smoother transition to industry. Female students particularly benefited, as the SLE promoted gender equality through equitable distribution of leadership and technical roles, showing early progress in reducing gender stereotypes. Collaboration with industry further inspired and offered fair opportunities for female students to advance in IT.

Educators: Faculty members and teaching assistants strengthened their pedagogical skills through active mentorship and facilitation. By guiding students in conflict resolution, team collaboration, and independent decision-making, educators refined their teaching methodologies, becoming more effective in addressing diverse student needs and providing meaningful, constructive feedback in a real-world project.

Industry: Industry professionals played a crucial role by offering mentorship, sharing practical insights, and creating valuable networking and career opportunities for the students. Their involvement

helped students stay informed about current industry trends and emerging technologies and provided inspiration through real-world success stories. Additionally, this collaboration reinforced partnerships between educational institutions and industry, while providing companies with valuable insights into future employees' skills and training needs, enabling the refinement of onboarding and professional development strategies.

Broader Societal Implications: This multi-stakeholder, collaborative approach contributed to educational equality, diversity, and practical skill development. By addressing gender imbalances and equipping students with real-world competencies, the SLE played a vital role in preparing future professionals for careers in STEAM fields.

Implications and way forward

The concept of the SLEs project aligns closely with the principles and priorities of open schooling as promoted by the European Commission in its efforts to enhance science education [4]. SLEs envisions open schools collaborating with various stakeholders to become catalysts for community well-being by fostering new local partnerships. This approach integrates all learning environments and educational levels, extending beyond formal education to incorporate non-formal and informal learning spaces, businesses, and civil society. Additionally, SLEs build on living lab practices for open schooling, empowering students to co-develop solutions to real-world challenges through active community engagement. Through this structured approach, SLEs create meaningful opportunities for problem-solving aligned with Europe's current policy agenda (e.g., the Green Deal, digital transformation, public health). These outcomes—enhanced collaboration, inclusion, and real-world engagement—underpin broader societal impact by enabling learners and institutions to co-create sustainable, innovation-driven communities.

In particular, the first phase of SLEs showcased several lessons learned for insights that can be used to implement large-scale learning ecologies successfully. SLEs contributed to making students reflect on gender stereotypes in STEAM and helped to deconstruct them through a dynamic exchange, e.g. where the students themselves adopted or presented roles and situations in their classroom and school context. The students applied real-life scientific instruments and techniques, moving from theoretical understanding to practical research experience. Moreover, our case studies' insights indicate that SLEs allowed the development of local connections between STEAM educators and various organizations that can actively facilitate opportunities for young learners. However, a possible constraint for successful adoption is the need for adequate time for facilitation, institutional support, and strong local partnerships among stakeholders. SLEs broadened children's perspectives by explicitly linking curriculum content and instruction methods to real-world applications, academic pathways, career opportunities, and create learning experiences and discussions that help identify students' interests, allowing for more responsive and engaging instruction. At a curriculum design level, our results indicate that the SLEs approach can support STEAM programs to better align with students' everyday interests, ensuring that program introductions and contexts are meaningful and relatable. Lastly, the SLEs approach helped

stakeholders to identify gaps in STEAM learning opportunities—including content domains, age groups, and experience levels—and the need to collaborate across communities to bridge these gaps. Building on insights from the pilot phase, future work will explore the long-term sustainability and scalability of these results.

Ethics Statement

This study was conducted as part of the TDT4290 - Customer Driven Project course at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU). The supervisors informed all participating students about the research purpose and students gave their informed consent for their anonymized learning artifacts to be used for research purposes. No personal or identifiable data were collected or stored. The project was carried out in accordance with ethical guidelines for educational research.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michail Giannakos: Writing – original draft. **Eleni Chatzidaki:** Writing – original draft. **Ioana Caraghiozov:** Writing – review & editing. **Evita Tasiopoulou:** Writing – review & editing. **Stefania Laneve:** Writing – review & editing. **Laura Mentini:** Writing – review & editing. **Pavlos Koulouris:** Writing – review & editing. **Georgios Mavromanolakis:** Writing – review & editing. **Liakopoulos Vasileios:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Eleni Chatzidaki NTNU reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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